

Cultural features of the of riddles in Uzbek and English languages

Nuriddinova Huriyat Baxtiyor qizi,

The teacher of Termez state Pedagogical institute

nuriddinova93@inbox.ru

Abstract: Riddles can be researched in many ways, specifically, metaphorical features by its grammatical rules. Lexical similarities between Uzbek and English riddles were examined in this paper, along with characteristics of riddles that have been viewed from various angles by scientists. There are similarities and differences within riddles in terms of their structure, articulation style, and content. The similarity implies that they are both the result of mythological and traditional creation. This article examines the similarities and differences between riddles written in two languages.

Key words: riddle, simile, antonym, grouping,

Introduction: As far as we are aware, riddles have been crafted since prehistoric times as a means of expressing prehistoric beliefs and lifestyles. F.I. Buslayev, a Russian linguist and folklorist, states that myths originated from the primitive ancestors' totemistic and animistic beliefs, which were prevalent when people's consciousness was first emerging. As a complex phenomenon, riddles are being researched by numerous linguists, scientists, and folklorists. However, we can also observe characteristics that remain unexplored. To solve the puzzles and decipher their meaning, one must be creative. Riddles aid in the reader's understanding of the intricate details because they are written in an everyday setting. When the riddles are examined historically, they date back 4,000 years.¹

One of the earliest riddles ever discovered dates to the 13th century BC and was inscribed on papyrus in ancient Egypt. These riddles' moral and philosophical consequences frequently put people's reasoning to the test.

Riddles are the foundation of people's long-held beliefs, vivid imaginations, and desires to learn about and comprehend the universe. He says the secret is to find hidden stuff. As a result, to determine the answer, one must carefully study the riddle's text, evaluate it, comprehend what is being said, and then attempt to deduce the answer by speculating on the meaning of the riddle's features and symbols. In this way, solving riddles fosters pupils' resourcefulness, flexibility, and intelligence.

¹ Z.Husainova, "O'zbek topishmoqlari", p21

Method of investigation and analysis: Because the solutions to riddles reflect the figurative character of life, which is true of riddles from all countries, a great deal of research has been done on riddles, and many literary works view riddles as an international genre. According to E.B.Taylor,² "the riddle appeared together with the proverb in the history of culture, and its heyday corresponds to the lower and middle stages of civilization", according to him, "the riddle is a traditional question-and-answer form that usually leads to dry humor. is not a modern word game, but an assignment in an ancient form that demanded a serious answer. The Sphinx's riddle serves as a prime illustration of this. The Sphinx was planned as a winged creature with a female body and a lion's head in Greek mythology. He made his home not far from Thebes. He questioned, "Who walks on four legs in the morning, two in the afternoon, and three in the evening?" and then executed those who were unable to respond. In the end, Oedipus becomes the king of Thebes after solving the riddle, stating: "Man crawls when he is a child, when he grows up he walks upright, when he is old he leans on a staff." Numerous academics have offered varying perspectives on riddles, such as: According to M.A. Rybnikova: "A riddle expresses a concrete object in the dialectic of its origin, function and life."³

F. I. Buslayev, another of these scientists, notes that "riddles appeared in times when human consciousness was just starting to spark."

The statement "Tabzugguq tabizdim" (I asked him a riddle) is another one that Makhmud Koshgari uses. This sentence illustrates how old the enigma is. "A riddle is a product of the nation's spiritual wealth and collective creativity, as are other genres of folk oral creativity: epics, fairy tales, songs, and proverbs," says Z. Husainova, who conducted a thorough study of Uzbek riddles in 1981. It always has a real foundation and is closely related to both natural phenomena and current facets of human social life. It displays a variety of items from the actual, material world that surrounds us. Every riddle is a unique piece of art with its own structure and meaning. Its exquisite figurative metaphors capture the core of philosophical, historical, and anthropological signs, concepts, and occurrences. Two categories of riddles are also studied: classic riddles and contemporary riddles. Standard riddles date back to the nation's distant past. Metaphorical analogies allow things that are not conceivable in classical riddles to be mixed. For instance, if we consider the "carrot" riddle from the "golden pile under the ground," the carrot's shape and color are compared to a pile and to gold, respectively. Thus, a golden pile would take the

² A.Taylor, "Riddle" 1943

³ M.A.Ribnikova, "Zagadki" Moskva,p6

place of the carrot if it were the solution to this riddles. The new riddles simply make reference to the present theme; they are based on the classic riddles.

Methodology of research: A close examination of the oral traditions of various peoples reveals a great deal of commonality in their riddles. Because people in that country, no matter what country they live in, place a high value on children's intelligence and upbringing. A closer look at one of the English folk riddles reveals that things are made by drawing comparisons between themselves and other individuals.

Little Nancy Etticoat in a white petticoat, and a red nose

The longer she stands, the shorter she grows (A candle)⁴

Nancy the Little Etticoat with a white coat and a crimson nose. It becomes shorter the longer you stand (A candle). If we compare Uzbek riddles with English riddles by grammatically, it is prominent to state the investigation of **metaphoric** sides. English riddles own the features of mostly questioning enigmas.

As an example,

I have cities but no houses,

I have mountains but no tees

I have water but no fish.

What am I? (A map)

Compared to this Uzbek riddles mostly they are composed with synonym and antonym words and in a word of wisdom. For example: “*Dengizi bor suvi yo’q, yo’llari bor izi yo’q.*”⁵ (in English: *it has sea but no water, it has roads but no trace*). There are some similarities of these riddles by structure which both of them address “sea, water; During the investigation we found such riddles that divided into

⁴ A.Taylor, “Riddle” 1943,p129-147

⁵ I.Avvalboyeva, “Bolalar uchun topishmoqlar”Zarcheckak,p5

traditional and modern riddles. In comparison with proverbs riddles hide something in it and to find the answer we should now to what it is resembled. For example in Uzbek there is one riddle “A gold pile underground-yer tagida oltin qoziq”, the answer of this riddle is “a carrot” and because the carrot is yellow it is resembled to gold, as the length it is liked to a pile.

Result: Explorations show that riddles own similarities and differences by forms, meaning, as well as grammatical structure. Under all types of riddles there lies myth, shows tradition and secret. “one of the efficient and common ways of methods is “comparison-typology method”.⁶ Comparison means that the genre, epic and image of one country comprise with other countries’ folklore.⁷ During the comparison we can see the other sides also, for example, different aspects: in Uzbek language there is one riddle “og’zi qora alomat, ichi qizil qiyomat”(mouth is a black sign, inside is a red doomsday). The answer of this riddle is the oven made by mud which reflected fire.⁸ In this place that’s turn to English riddle about *a car pool* “What kind of pool can’t you swim in?”⁹. A pool is a small body of water. It can also refer to a common supply of something, such as money, that can be used by a number of people. It is shown that money is like a pool, because it is used by everyone, pool is liked to people swimming in it using money. In contrast, if a car is being a pool it is resembled that when people drive together in the same car to save gas and money, it is called a car pool. To compare with two languages riddles, English ones mostly refers to questioning, meaningly they are formed in questions. As an example to this “*What helps you keep your teeth together?*”(toothpaste). Toothpaste is the substance we use when we brush our teeth. Paste also refers to glue, which makes things stick together.¹⁰ In Uzbek riddles we mostly face myth, dilemma or paradox. “Ikki aka uka yashaydi, bir birini ko’rmaydi” (live two brothers, don’t see each other), this riddle is a good example of paradox and the answer is “eyes”. Riddles are divided into two types by structure: *prose* and *poetry*. Prose riddles amounts the minority than poetry ones. Poetry riddles are structured in poetry rhyme: *To’rtidir uning oyog’i, Temir mixli tuyog’i, Manzilga yetishtirar, Toshdan qattiq tuyog’i.(ot)*; in this riddle the rhymes are *oyog’i, tuyog’i*. People have been making riddles for centuries. New to the social scene, riddles concerning objects and occasions were also developed. Thus, the tractor, gramophone, radio, television, train, automobile, tram, and

⁶ Jo’rayev M. Folklorshunoslik asoslari. -T.: "Fan", 2009. - B. 154. (190)

⁷ Shu asar

⁸ Topishmoqlar,129

⁹ 101 American English riddles,p4

¹⁰ Shown book.

airplane that invaded our life, a number of puzzles pertaining to the lightbulb, phone, and satellite were developed: *Kechasi oftobdek, Kunduzi koptokdek. (Lampochka.) Qush emas, qanoti bor, Chiroyli savlati bor. Uchsa lochin yetolmas, Tolmas zo‘r quw ati bor. (Samolyot). (Similar to the nighttime sun, Similar to a ball in the daytime. (Bulbs.) It has wings, thus it's not a bird. It looks quite nice. A falcon is not able to fly. One of his strongest suit is airplane.*¹¹

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¹¹ Oxunjon Safarov, “O‘zbek xalq og‘zaki ijodi”, «Musiqa» nashriyoti Toshkent 2010,b289

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